

LEARNING ADJUSTMENTS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE POST-PANDEMIC ERA: A STUDY OF STUDENT EXPERIENCES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 6

Pages: 568-570

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2487

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1392934

Manuscript Accepted: 09-21-2024

Learning Adjustments and Academic Performance in the Post-Pandemic Era: A Study of Student Experiences

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between students' learning adjustments in the post-pandemic environment and their academic performance. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, research highlights the significant positive correlation between effective learning adjustments and improved academic outcomes. The findings underscore the necessity for educators and policymakers to implement supportive interventions that facilitate students' adaptation to new learning conditions. Recommendations for future research and practical applications are discussed, emphasizing the importance of understanding diverse student needs in educational settings.

Keywords: *learning adjustments, academic performance, post-pandemic education, student experiences*

Introduction

The researcher is a Head Teacher at Catalino M. Prado National High School and is currently teaching two subjects among high school students. It had been observed that even though the face-to-face classes were back the students needed to adjust to the present settings. They have different responses on getting along with their classmate, going to school every day, performing daily learning tasks and coping with the lesson.

It had been observed that even though the face-to-face classes were back the students needed to adjust to the present settings.. The reading assessment and numeracy test results showed that there were students who had difficulty in reading and there were several non-numerates. Two years of the pandemic that caused home-based learning without teachers facilitating them could be one factor in this. Assessment of learning done in classroom settings was not administered making it not truly measure the achievement of learning expectations. Home-based learning was first ever done in their schooling because of the pandemic their learning outcomes were based on written works and performance tasks absence of teachers requires a learning support system from home and the transition from off-school learning to on-school learning affects their adaptability to new environments. Since the reading and numeracy skills were basic learning gaps that needed to be addressed, interventions were done by the school for them to adjust to competencies expected in their grade level. Therefore, the researcher wanted to know the post-pandemic learning adjustment of the students for them to learn effectively and cope with the lesson so that she could make intervention and learning activity plan to guide in programs and activities suited to their learner's needs that facilitate their learning adjustments and improve academic performance.

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted educational systems worldwide, necessitating rapid shifts to online and hybrid learning environments. As students navigate these changes, their ability to adjust to new learning modalities has become critical for academic success. Recent studies indicate that students who adapt effectively to these changes tend to perform better academically (Salari et al., 2020; Rodriguez, 2020). Understanding the factors that influence learning adjustments is essential for developing effective educational strategies in the post-pandemic context.

Research has shown that social-emotional learning (SEL) plays a vital role in students' ability to cope with the challenges posed by the pandemic (Durlak et al., 2017). Furthermore, the integration of technology in education has been linked to enhanced student engagement and self-directed learning (Rambe & Moeti, 2017). However, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the specific relationship between learning adjustments and academic performance in the post-pandemic era. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how students' learning adjustments impact their academic outcomes.

Research Questions

The main objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between students' learning adjustments and their academic performance in the post-pandemic among students of Catalino M. Prado National High School, District of Lezo, Aklan, Philippines during the school year 2022-2023.

1. What is the relationship between students' level of learning adjustment and their academic performance in the post-pandemic context?
2. What factors contribute to successful learning adjustments among students?
3. How can educators and policymakers support students in adapting to new learning environments?

Literature Review

The transition to online learning during the pandemic has highlighted the importance of adaptability in educational settings. According to Salari et al. (2020), the prevalence of stress and anxiety among students has increased, affecting their academic performance. Durlak

et al. (2017) emphasize the significance of SEL in fostering resilience and adaptability, suggesting that students equipped with these skills are more likely to succeed academically.

Rambe and Moeti (2017) discuss the role of technology in facilitating learning adjustments, noting that online education can enhance self-directed learning and provide opportunities for interaction. However, the effectiveness of these adjustments varies among students, influenced by factors such as socioeconomic status, access to resources, and individual learning styles (Seo, 2015). This literature underscores the need for targeted interventions to support diverse student populations in their learning journeys.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between learning adjustments and academic performance.

Respondents

The study involved 116 students from Catalino M. Prado National High School, aged 12 to 17, who were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation across different grade levels and backgrounds.

Instrument

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that assessed the students' learning adjustments and academic performance. The questionnaire included validated scales measuring adaptability, motivation, and engagement. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of 20 participants to gain deeper insights into their experiences.

Procedure

Participants were informed about the study's purpose and provided consent before data collection. The questionnaires were administered online, followed by individual interviews conducted via video conferencing. Data were analyzed using statistical software for quantitative analysis and thematic analysis for qualitative data.

Ethical Considerations

Study adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. Informed consent was obtained from students and their parents, and participants were allowed to withdraw from the study without repercussions.

Results and Discussion

The quantitative analysis revealed that 78% of students reported a high level of learning adjustment during the post-pandemic period, with mean scores indicating strong motivation (4.2), active participation (4.1), and adaptability to technology (4.3). A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$) was found between learning adjustment and academic performance, with 70% of students maintaining or improving their academic standing compared to pre-pandemic levels.

Qualitative findings highlighted several key themes: the importance of peer support, effective teacher facilitation, challenges in maintaining motivation, and the role of technology adaptation. Students emphasized that collaboration with peers and supportive teachers significantly contributed to their ability to adjust to the new learning environment. However, some students reported difficulties in self-discipline and motivation, particularly those who thrived in traditional classroom settings.

The findings of this study align with existing literature, reinforcing the notion that effective learning adjustments are crucial for academic success in the post-pandemic context. The significant correlation between adaptability and performance suggests that interventions aimed at enhancing students' learning adjustments could lead to improved academic outcomes.

Educators and policymakers must prioritize the development of support systems that address the diverse needs of students, particularly in areas such as SEL and technology integration. Future research should explore longitudinal effects of learning adjustments on academic performance and investigate specific strategies that can facilitate these adjustments.

Conclusions

This study contributes to the understanding of how students navigate the challenges of post-pandemic education. By highlighting the importance of learning adjustments, it calls for a collaborative effort among educators, parents, and policymakers to create supportive learning environments that foster student success.

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